

SCALE-BRIDGING FATIGUE ASSESSMENT OF STEELS – FROM PRODUCTION TO PERFORMANCE

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In times of increasing energy and material costs, the precise monitoring of machined parts is crucial for reliably achieving the maximum service life under fatigue loading. The conditions and states of components need to be accurately observed starting from the manufacturing process over the service time to maintenance and end-of-life. This paper gives an overview of fatigue research on steels, focusing on the improvement of production processes and non-destructive evaluation of deformation/damage states with respect to increasing fatigue requirements. The research work links production engineering and materials science and engineering. The development of approaches for robust online evaluation for forming and machining processes is presented. Moreover, the development and validation of concepts for evaluating damage evolution under relevant service conditions are discussed, focusing on machined parts, brazed joints and nuclear power plant steels. The mechanism-oriented consideration of the influencing variables and cause-effect relationships is of decisive importance, since distinguishing between superimposing effects that occur presents a central challenge in the identification of robust correlations.

Keywords: Metal fatigue, Forming, Machining, Fatigue life evaluation

INTRODUCTION

Failure due to fatigue-related damage is one of the most serious problems in present-day mechanical engineering. In order to ensure maximum utilisation of the service life of manufactured components from the point of view of increasing raw material and energy prices, it is of immense importance to monitor the components throughout the entire product life cycle, from manufacture and utilisation to the end of service life. In the following, it is illustrated how the service life to be reached can already be significantly influenced by forming, cutting and joining manufacturing processes and how this affects practical applications.

STRATEGIES FOR ROBUST ONLINE EVALUATION OF DESIRABLE SURFACE INTEGRITY DURING FLOW FORMING

By means of flow forming (**FIGURE 1a**) of metastable austenitic steel tubes, the production of axially symmetrical components for a broad range of engineering applications is possible (Runge [1]). Under appropriate thermal conditions, plastic deformation of these steels not only reduces the

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wall thickness of final products, but also phase transformation from austenite into martensite occurs for metastable austenitic steels (Sohrabi et al. [2], Angel [3]). **FIGURE 1b** illustrates the geometry and dimensions of AISI 304L specimens used for analyses. The initial 4 mm wall thickness was reduced with infeed depths of 1.0, 2.0 and 3.0 mm in each flow forming step. Starting from the initial condition, “IC” (metastable austenite), flow forming operations were performed to produce three forming zones (FZ 1, 2 and 3). Each forming zone corresponds to a plastic deformation state with a defined amount of strain-induced α' -martensite. Feed rates of the roller tool of 6 and 60 mm/s were used during the flow forming process to produce two different specimens. This allows the production of final components with specific magnetic and mechanical properties **FIGURE 1c**.

FIGURE 1 Specimen manufacture: a) flow forming process; b) geometry and dimensions (in mm); c) final workpieces. IC: Initial condition, forming zones (FZ) 1–3, AISI 304L.

In flow forming processes, the two aspects involved in the adjustment of surface integrity play an important role. One of them is the topography made up of surface roughness and the other one is the surface layer characteristics. This includes plastic deformation, residual stresses, hardness and especially phase changes (Black and Kohser [4]). The development of strategies for robust online evaluation and adjustment of surface integrity requires the development of reliable non-destructive measuring systems, such as magnetic Barkhausen noise (MBN) analysis (Baak et al. [5]). **FIGURE 2** summarizes the results of α' -martensite amount, hardness, residual stresses, roughness and maximum amplitude of MBN (M_{max}) (Rozo et al. [6]).

FIGURE 2 Multi-technique characterization and correlation between magnetic Barkhausen noise, α' -martensite amount, hardness, residual stresses and roughness on different forming conditions (IC, FZ 1-3) of flow-formed specimens produced with feed rates of 6 and 60 mm/min of the roller tool, AISI 304L [6].

The measurements were recorded on the different forming conditions of the two specimens produced, as described above. The behaviour of roughness is highly dependent on the feed rate of

the roller tool, since the distance between the microgrooves produced during flow forming determines the roughness. The compressive residual stresses increase with the deformation and are slightly higher on components produced with lower feed rates. Finally, the results reveal the increment of the α' -martensite amount and the hardness with the deformation, as well as the influence of the feed rate of the tool. The slower the movement of the roller tool, the greater the amount of martensite formed, due to the higher plastic deformation. It can be concluded that the α' -martensite measurements are well correlated with the non-destructive $M_{\max}$ measurements and therefore the micromagnetic measuring systems are suitable for the online monitoring of the surface integrity, which has a major influence on the fatigue performance of the produced part (Rozo et al. [7]).

DAMAGE-CONTROLLED FORMING PROCESSES

Besides the adjustment of surface integrity parameters today's metal forming is not only used for changing the shape of materials, but also for the precise adjustment of product properties and capability (Tekkaya et al. [8]). The features of massive formed steel parts are dependent on forming-induced damage which nucleates and evolves before failure occurs. Therefore, knowledge about the forming-induced damage has to be developed, preferentially determined in non-destructive measurements, to separate these production-induced impairments from the fatigue induced.

In order to separate these effects, instrumented fatigue tests of 16MnCrS5 specimens with different shoulder opening angles 2α were performed. The shoulder opening angle 2α of the die forward rod-extrusion was identified as a forming parameter that significantly influences forming-induced damage on the centre axis. The tests were carried out intermittently by removing the specimen at specified intervals, measuring the electrical resistance, and then continuing after the specimen had been reinstalled. Previous studies have shown that in defined areas of formed components with shoulder opening angles of 30° and 90° , the microstructure differs only in forming-induced pre-damage. Absolute values of the electrical resistance R of specimens (4 of each configuration) before fatigue testing (initial state) are shown in **FIGURE 3 a**). Those specimens were then analysed at 25%, 50% and 75% of the fatigue life using the testing setup for resistance measurement. The normalised results are plotted in **FIGURE 3 b**) for one exemplary specimen of each shoulder opening angle.

In TABLE 1 the difference in hardness, density and pore area fraction (SEM investigations) of both configurations are shown, especially the latter is defining the pre-damage and thus the higher electrical resistance of 90° specimens in **FIGURE 3 a**) can be assigned. Until 50% fatigue life, a slight ΔR increase is noticeable for both configurations. However, the increase is greater in the less pre-damaged 30° specimen from 25% to 50% which is attributed to earlier micro-crack formation. A significant increase occurs from 50% to 75% lifetime, for 30° to 2.0% and 90° to 1.6%. Failure occurs when a defined value of total damage is accumulated. The total damage is a sum of forming-induced pre-damage and fatigue damage, i.e. less forming-induced pre-damaged 30° specimen allows more fatigue damage compared to 90° specimen. Thus, a correlation between the electrical resistance and the fatigue damage can also be demonstrated.

TABLE 1 Pore area fraction, hardness and density of forward rod-extruded 16MnCrS5 specimens with a shoulder opening angle 2α of 30° (left) and 90° (right).

Pore area fraction	0.0059%	0.0234%
Hardness	198 HV1	201 HV1
Density	7.8247 g/cm ³	7.8215 g/cm ³

FIGURE 3 Electrical resistance of forward rod-extruded 16MnCrS5 specimens for different shoulder opening angles (a) (Hering et al. [9], Lückner et al. [10]) and relative change in electrical resistance versus normalised fatigue life (b) [10].

CAPABILITY OF DEEP-DRILLED COMPONENTS UNDER QUASI-STATIC AND CYCLIC COMPRESSION

Machining processes have an influence on the performance of produced parts. For instance, when steels are machined at high cutting speeds and feed rates, undesirable microstructural changes can occur as a consequence of high thermal and mechanical loads. A particularly notable example of this is the formation of white etching layers (WEL) during cutting. These layers are nanocrystalline, hard, and brittle and usually have a thickness in the range of $t = 1$ to $10 \mu\text{m}$, though higher thicknesses have also been reported (Brown et al. [11], Zhang et al. [12]). WEL are oftentimes considered to have a detrimental impact on a component's fatigue life, by promoting the formation and propagation of cracks (La Monaca et al. [13], Liao et al. [14]). However, to date, the influence of WEL on the performance of components remains a highly controversial topic (Stampfer et al. [15]).

The impact of WEL on the capability of boring and trepanning association (BTA) deep-drilled components is evaluated. For this purpose, an instrumented testing procedure was developed, inspired by the tube flattening test (DIN EN ISO 8492). This procedure allows for assessing the performance of deep-drilled components under quasi-static and cyclic loads. An illustration of the specimens and the setup used is depicted in **FIGURE 4a**, exemplary results for an instrumented constant amplitude test are given in **FIGURE 4b**. The evolution of residual stresses was evaluated intermittently by X-ray diffraction and magnetic Barkhausen noise analysis. In quasi-static testing, it was found that crack initiation occurred at significantly lower displacements, when WEL were present at the deep-drilled surfaces (Strodick et al. [16]). Further information on this research is provided in (Strodick et al. [17]).

FIGURE 4 a) Specimen extraction and setup employed for cyclic testing of deep-drilled AISI 4140 components; b) Result of instrumented constant amplitude tests: residual stress, max. magnetic Barkhausen noise (MBN) amplitude and dye penetration testing after $N = 60,000$ cycles [16].

CORROSION FATIGUE AND FATIGUE IN VHCF REGIME OF BRAZED AISI 304L JOINTS

High-temperature vacuum brazed steel joints with nickel-based filler metals are often subjected to superimposed mechanical, thermal and corrosive stresses during operation (Way et al. [18], Bobzin et al. [19]). Examples are exhaust gas heat exchangers, honeycomb seals in gas turbines or injection moulding tools (Boretius [20]). The microstructure of brazed seams is of central importance for the service life of these highly loaded joints and is therefore subject of research (Yang et al. [21]). It is influenced by selected process parameters, the base material, geometric influences and the filler metal used in terms of its chemical composition. Since melting point lowering elements such as boron, silicon and phosphorus have to be used, the formation of complex brittle phases such as

borides, silicides and phosphides play an important role in crack initiation and propagation. Additionally, these brittle phases causing micro-galvanic corrosion, reducing the service life of these joints in corrosive environments.

Although brazing technologies are state of the art for many industrial applications, microstructure- and mechanism-based fatigue assessments of brazed joints considering service relevant conditions are not common. New test concepts for brazed joints are developed and validated with the aim of evaluating the deformation and damage evolution in the very high cycle fatigue (VHCF) range or in service relevant corrosive media, like the synthetic exhaust gas condensate K2.2. **Figure 5** shows an application-oriented test setup consisting of a corrosion cell, a three-electrode system for electrochemical measuring and extensometers integrated in a servo-hydraulic testing system (Otto et al. [22], Schmiedt et al. [23]).

FIGURE 5 Test setup for corrosion fatigue tests on brazed AISI 304L joints [22,23].

Results on three high-temperature vacuum brazed AISI 304L joints (BJ) are presented which were produced with the following filler metal, brazing temperature T_B and dwell time t_B :

- BJ1: ST07 (Ni-7Cr-7.5Si-4Fe-1.5B), $T_B = 1160\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $t_B = 40\text{ min}$
- BJ2: BNi-2 (Ni-7Cr-4.5Si-3.2B-3Fe), $T_B = 1050\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $t_B = 2\text{ min}$
- BJ3: VZ2177 (Ni-25Cr-6P-1.5Si-0.5B), $T_B = 1100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $t_B = 5\text{ min}$

Since the high brazing temperature and dwell time of BJ1 resulted in high grain sizes it showed a comparatively high ductility. The fracture morphology of BJ1 in **Figure 6** can roughly be divided into a fatigue fracture area (I) and a force fracture area (II), with most of the fracture occurring inside the brittle boride-phases containing diffusion zone above and below the brazed seam (Otto et al. [24]).

FIGURE 6 Fracture morphology of a brazed AISI 304L joint BJ1 after constant amplitude tests at 320 MPa failed at $3.2 \cdot 10^5$ cycles, with fatigue fracture areas (I) and a forced fracture area (II) [24].

Figure 7 shows, besides others, the course of the measured free electrochemical open circuit potential E_{OCP} during corrosion fatigue, which depends in the case of stainless steels mainly on the non-passivated free surface exposed to the medium. Increasing strain during the first cycles of the test causes the passive layer to break up at various points and then to repassivate. In the following, intrusions and extrusions cause smaller fractures in the passive layer which immediately start to repassivate. Finally, microcracks and later macrocracks begin to form, exposing non-passivated surfaces, which leads to a significant drop in E_{OCP} .

FIGURE 7 Measurement of the electrochemical open circuit potential (E_{OCP}) and strain values for a constant amplitude test at 300 MPa in the corrosive medium K2.2 for AISI 304L BJ1 [24].

The brazed joint BJ2 shows a better fatigue performance than BJ3 in air conditions in the high cycle fatigue (HCF) regime and likewise in the corrosive medium K2.2 up to $5 \cdot 10^5$ cycles, as exemplarily shown for a maximum stress σ_{max} of 212 MPa (**Figure 8a**). At higher numbers of cycles to failure and longer test durations, the superimposed corrosive loading only results in a significant fatigue life reduction for BJ2 due to boride formation and chromium depletion in the austenitic base material. The improved corrosion fatigue performance as a result of the optimized chemical composition of the filler metal used for BJ3 is shown in **FIGURE 8a** for a maximum stress σ_{max} of 195 MPa. The frequency-dependent fatigue life and cyclic deformation behaviour of BJ3 are comparable in air and corrosive medium, as exemplarily presented for a maximum stress σ_{max} of 212 MPa for fatigue tests with test frequencies f of 0.1 and 10 Hz (**Figure 8b**). In this context, the application of a self-designed extensometer for strain measurements with a gauge length of 5 mm ($L_{0,5}$) in the corrosion cell and with a gauge length of 3 mm ($L_{0,3}$) in air allows the evaluation of the local deformation behaviour in the area of the brazed joints (**Figure 8a and b**).

FIGURE 8 Total mean strains a) for the brazed AISI 304L joints BJ2 and BJ3 in corrosive medium K2.2 and b) for brazed joint BJ3 at test frequencies of 0.1, 10 and 1,000 Hz in air and corrosive medium K2.2.

To improve the mechanism-based understanding of the test frequency influence on the fatigue behaviour of brazed joints, fatigue tests in the VHCF regime in air at 1 kHz were added. Increasing the test frequency by a factor of 100 increases the number of cycles to failure by 2 to 3 decades. Strain measurements to characterise the deformation behaviour during fatigue testing at 1 kHz on the high-frequency resonant fatigue system (Rumul Gigaforte, 50 kN load cell) were performed using a high-speed camera system (GOM Aramis HS 6400 / SRX-8GB) (Figure 8b).

In summary, the corrosive-mechanical properties and therefore the service life of brazed joints are strongly dependent on the microstructure, which is influenced by the filler metal and the brazing process parameters. Furthermore, due to time-dependent corrosion mechanism, the test duration has a significant influence on whether corrosive or mechanical damage dominates the service life. Therefore, the selection of an appropriate test frequency is of great importance to separate corrosion, fatigue and corrosion-fatigue mechanisms.

NONDESTRUCTIVE TECHNIQUES FOR FATIGUE LIFE EVALUATION OF NUCLEAR POWER PLANT COMPONENTS

As nuclear power plants (NPP) age and operators strive to achieve the longest possible lifetimes to meet increasing energy demands, methods and concepts for evaluating the remaining fatigue life of materials and components can become valuable tools in meeting these requirements. In an NPP components are commonly exposed to superimpositions from corrosive, thermal and mechanical loadings. Metastable austenitic steels are commonly used in powerplants as a material for pressurised hot water pipelines (Chopra and Stevens [25]). In initial state these steels have a paramagnetic austenitic crystal structure, but under mechanical loading phase transformation to ferromagnetic α' -martensite can occur. Therefore, magnetic methods are used to examine these steels (Smaga et al. [26]). **FIGURE 9** gives an instrumented fatigue testing setup in the presence of an electrolyte and results from a strain increase test combining magnetic and electrochemical methods.

FIGURE 9 a) Testing setup to evaluate NDT parameters with an electrolyte present, b) results from strain increase test (Donnerbauer et al. [27]), AISI 347.

Exact description of testing parameters can be taken from [27], where results have already been published. The signal from Hall voltage is best suited to describe the cyclic strain hardening behaviour. Onset of Hall voltage increase fits well to the stress amplitude starting to show a nonlinear increase. Therefore, the observed hardening corresponds to phase transformation from austenite to ferromagnetic α' -martensite. The absolute signal of open circuit potential is well suited to indicate macro crack growth, since the signal decreases if free surfaces are not yet passivated. To be able to use the electrochemical signal for short-time evaluation procedure StrainLife (Acosta et al. [28], Bill et al. [29]) the signals amplitude was introduced. This or other NDT signals can now be inputs for S-N-curve calculations, showing that NDT methods can be great alternatives to mechanical input sizes. On the one hand, because they can have access to different microstructural information, and on the other hand, because they often provide much better accessibility. This can be particularly important for components under operating conditions such as the use of liquid media.

CONCLUSIONS

This work has explored various aspects of material and component behaviour in the context of mechanical engineering, with a particular focus on how manufacturing processes, damage control, and material properties influence the performance and integrity of components.

Flow forming revealed that the surface integrity of components can be significantly influenced by manufacturing processes, such as flow forming, leading to changes in phase transformations, hardness, and surface roughness. The use of non-destructive measuring systems, including magnetic Barkhausen noise analysis, offers a reliable method for monitoring and adjusting desirable surface integrity, crucial for enhancing the fatigue performance of the components.

Damage-controlled forming processes were investigated, demonstrating the importance of understanding the impact of forming-induced damage on components fatigue performance. The correlation between electrical resistance measurements and fatigue damage provided valuable insights into the progression of damage, highlighting the significance of non-destructive testing methods.

Also, the impact of machining processes, specifically focusing on white etching layers formed during cutting is addressed. The formation of these layers can significantly affect a component's fatigue life, emphasising the need for understanding and mitigating such effects.

Furthermore, the corrosion fatigue and very high cycle fatigue (VHCF) of brazed joints was investigated. The choice of filler metal and process parameters played a crucial role in determining the microstructure and, consequently, the capability of brazed joints. The research emphasized the importance of selecting appropriate test frequencies to distinguish between corrosion, fatigue, and corrosion-fatigue mechanisms, ultimately affecting the service life of these joints.

Finally, the paper extended its scope to nuclear power plant components, emphasising the significance of non-destructive testing methods in evaluating the remaining fatigue life. Metastable austenitic steels were examined using magnetic and electrochemical methods to provide insights into cyclic strain hardening and macro crack growth, enabling a better understanding of material behaviour and aiding in fatigue life evaluation.

In summary, this paper highlights the scale-bridging interplay of manufacturing processes, material properties, and damage mechanisms in determining the performance and integrity of components in mechanical engineering. It highlights the importance of non-destructive testing techniques in evaluating and predicting component behaviour, offering valuable insights for improving the design and longevity of engineered systems in various industrial applications.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors gratefully acknowledge the funding by the German Research Foundation (DFG) for the subprojects B01 and C01 within the Collaborative Research Center CRC/Transregio 188 “Damage controlled forming processes” (project no. 278868966), the priority program SPP 2086 “Surface conditioning in machining processes” (project no. 401539425) and the priority program SPP 2183 “Property-controlled forming processes” (project no. 424335026), moreover for the project no. 264915567 and 408904168. This research was also funded by the Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection (BMUV) within the framework of the project “Microstructure-based determination of the maximum service life for corrosion fatigue-loaded materials and components of nuclear technology”, part II, project no.

1501610A, 1501610B, 1501610C, 1501610D and RS1594E. The authors thank the German Research Foundation and the Ministry of Culture and Science of North Rhine-Westphalia (MKW RW) for their financial support within the major research instrumentation program for the “XRD-system” (Bruker D8 Discover, project no. 383863415), the “High-frequency resonant fatigue testing system” (Rumul Gigaforte 50, project no. 424760282) and the “High-speed camera system” (GOM Aramis HS 6400, project no. 424852613).

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